

DACEM

Digitising Academic Catalogues for Enhanced Mobility

WP 2. Course Catalogues mapping and technical state of the art
at European HEIs

A comprehensive mapping of implementation avenues and challenges on online CCs

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Executive Summary

This synthetic report brings together the findings of three complementary research activities conducted under Work Package 2 of the DACEM (Digitising Academic Catalogues for Enhanced Mobility) project. The three activities: a systematic mapping of course catalogue practices across eight European higher education systems (A2.1), qualitative focus groups and interviews with 230 stakeholders at nine partner universities (A2.2), and two large-scale quantitative surveys involving more than 55,000 Erasmus+ students together with a dedicated HEI staff survey (A2.3); collectively constitute the most comprehensive evidence base currently available on the state of course catalogues (CCs) within the European Higher Education Area (EHEA).

CCs are not peripheral administrative documents. They are the primary interface for decision-making between students and institutions in the context of Erasmus+ mobility. Before a student sets foot on a foreign campus, the CC is the first and often only window through which they assess whether a host institution can support their academic trajectory. The quality, reliability and accessibility of that window directly determine whether students apply, whether Learning Agreements are correctly drafted, and whether credits are ultimately recognised.

Yet across all three research methods, the evidence converges on a remarkably consistent diagnosis: CCs are formally compliant with Bologna Process and Erasmus Charter for Higher Education (ECHE) requirements, but they are operationally inadequate for the needs of mobility students. They are technically available but often unreliable. They are published online but fragmented across multiple platforms and are hard to navigate. They exist in national languages but lack sufficient English-language content for incoming students. They meet formal deadlines but are updated too frequently or not at all, sometimes at the wrong times in the mobility calendar, leading to Learning Agreement amendments and credit recognition failures.

Key Quantitative Signals

As the reports from activities 2.1 and 2.2 measure quantitative data, key metrics have been extracted solely from the activity 2.3 report, as reflected in Table 1.

Table 1: Key quantitative signals

3.79/5	Average importance score for 'availability of matching, recognisable courses' as a pull factor for mobility destination choice (XV ESN survey, N=14,483). This is the highest institutional pull factor recorded.
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42%	Proportion of Erasmus+ students who had to alter their course plans upon arrival at the host institution, a direct consequence of inaccurate or unstable CC information.
14 ECTS	Average number of credits that students need to adjust upon arrival, out of an initial Learning Agreement averaging 33 ECTS, representing a 42% revision rate by volume.
28/30	Average ECTS recognised vs. completed during mobility: students complete approximately 30 ECTS but only 28 are recognised, reflecting a structural gap in credit transfer.
2.6%	Share of students reporting zero credit recognition upon return, an extreme outcome that points to fundamental CC failures in a minority of cases.
3.71/5	The average student satisfaction score for 'accessibility and completeness of the course catalogue' at host institutions is adequate but consistently lower than the highest-rated ECHE services.
20.7%	Share of Erasmus+ students never informed of their rights under the Erasmus Student Charter, highlighting broader information provision gaps in which CCs play a role.

Core Findings

Three systemic inadequacies cut across all three reports:

- the compliance–usability gap: CCs meet formal requirements (ECTS alignment, online publication, basic structure) but fail at the level of practical usability for mobility students. Being 'technically available' is not the same as being 'reliably useful'.
- temporal instability: CCs are published but updated late; courses listed are sometimes cancelled; information becomes outdated before students arrive. This temporal unreliability directly drives the 42% Learning Agreement amendment rate.
- language barriers: multilingual provision (particularly English) is systematically inadequate across all eight partner countries, with even institutions rated well on structural indicators often providing only partial or no English-language course descriptions.

Beyond these three primary inadequacies, the research identifies two further structural challenges:

- Institutional and national fragmentation, which means no common operational standard exists despite ECTS providing a shared credit framework.
- A fundamental design mismatch, whereby CCs are built for domestic degree students but relied upon by incoming international students navigating an unfamiliar system from a distance.

Recommendations Overview

The evidence base supports five categories of intervention:

- (1) Review and standardisation of CC content through a common European template with mandatory and recommended fields considering the needs of mobility students.
- (2) Governance improvements: clear update protocols, timestamps, user-reporting mechanisms, and freeze periods before mobility application deadline.
- (3) Digital modernisation, including mobile-first design, advanced search and filtering, and interoperability with EWP and OLA systems.
- (4) Full English-language provision for all mobility-relevant CC content.
- (5) The development of a European CC aggregation platform that provides a single point of access for students and coordinators across all participating HEIs.

1. Introduction and Project Context

1.1 The DACEM Project

DACEM (Digitising Academic Catalogues for Enhanced Mobility) is a European cooperation project funded under the Erasmus+ programme. Its central aim is to improve the quality, accessibility and interoperability of online course catalogues at Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) across Europe, with particular emphasis on supporting student mobility within the Erasmus+ framework. The project brings together nine partner organisations from eight countries, combining deep institutional expertise with the pan-European reach of the Erasmus Student Network (ESN).

Work Package 2 (WP2) is dedicated to mapping the current landscape of course catalogue (CC) practices and establishing a robust evidence base for the technical and policy recommendations that will guide the subsequent development work. WP2 is structured around three successive activities: a documentary mapping of existing CC systems and practices (A2.1); qualitative research through interviews and focus groups with institutional staff and students (A2.2); and quantitative survey research at both local and European scale (A2.3). This synthetic report integrates the findings of all three activities.

1.2 What Is a Course Catalogue?

A course catalogue (CC), also referred to as a course guide or course directory, is an institutional document, increasingly in digital form, that provides structured information about the courses offered by a higher education institution. At its most basic, a CC lists available courses with their titles, codes, credit values and scheduling information. At its most advanced, it provides comprehensive academic and logistical information enabling students to make fully informed enrolment decisions, also for mobility students.

In the context of student mobility, the CC plays a particularly critical role. For incoming Erasmus+ students, it is typically the first and primary resource through which they identify courses, assess alignment with their home-institution degree requirements, and draft the Learning Agreement (LA), the legally binding document that governs credit recognition. The quality and reliability of CC information thus have direct downstream consequences for LA stability, credit recognition outcomes, and overall student experience.

The Erasmus Charter for Higher Education (ECHE, European Commission 2021) explicitly requires institutions to publish and regularly update their CCs well in advance of mobility periods. The ECTS Users' Guide (2015) specifies minimum content expectations. Despite these requirements, this report documents substantial variation in CC quality across and

within European countries, with the gap between formal compliance and practical usability as the central challenge for the field.

1.3 Research Design and Methodology

The three WP2 activities deploy complementary research methodologies to build a multi-layered picture of the CC landscape:

- **A2.1 Course Catalogue Mapping:** Systematic documentary analysis of CC systems and practices in France, Greece, Spain, Portugal, Slovenia, Hungary, Estonia and Czechia. Each country team examined multiple institutions, identifying generic examples, best-practice cases, and recurring problems. The analysis was structured around: institutional requirements for operating CCs; use cases and stakeholder processes; existing software solutions and platforms; and a country-by-country comparative summary.
- **A2.2 Focus Groups and Interviews:** Qualitative research conducted between May and October 2024, involving 230 participants across nine partner universities. Two research instruments were deployed: structured interviews with Erasmus+ coordinators and institutional staff responsible for CC management and focus group discussions with international and incoming exchange students. Data were analysed thematically.
- **A2.3 Surveys on Course Catalogues:** Quantitative research combining four data sources: the XV ESN survey (conducted May–July 2023; N=17,855 Erasmus+ students from a total of N=22,775); the XVI ESN survey (conducted May–August 2025; N=6,975 Erasmus+ students); a short-scale DACEM bridging survey (October 2024; N=195 students from DACEM partner institutions); and a dedicated HEI staff survey (February–December 2025) targeting academic and administrative staff directly involved in mobility management.

1.4 Structure of This Report

Following this introduction, the report proceeds as follows:

- Section 2 presents the stakeholder ecosystem for course catalogues.
- Section 3 presents the national CC landscape as documented in A2.1, including country profiles, process analysis and good-practice examples.
- Section 4 presents the qualitative findings from A2.2, covering both cross-partner themes and institution-specific insights
- Section 5 presents the quantitative survey findings from A2.3 covering student perspectives (pre-departure, in-mobility and post-return) as well as HEI staff perspectives

- Section 6 synthesises findings across all three reports through five cross-cutting analytical themes.
- Section 7 presents the consolidated recommendations.
- Section 8 concludes with implications for the DACEM project and the wider policy context.

2. Stakeholder Landscape

CCs serve a diverse ecosystem of stakeholders whose needs and use patterns are often in tension with one another. A clear understanding of this landscape is essential to diagnosing the current shortcomings of CC systems and designing solutions that genuinely serve all relevant users. This section maps the stakeholder landscape as documented across the three WP2 activity reports.

2.1 Internal Institutional Stakeholders

2.1.1 Management and Administrative Staff

University administrators carry responsibility for the creation, updating and distribution of CCs. They must ensure that catalogue content is accurate, up-to-date, and compliant with institutional, national and international standards, including ECHE requirements and national accreditation frameworks. In many institutions, administrative responsibility is fragmented between the central level (responsible for institutional platforms and overall timelines) and the faculty or departmental level (responsible for the actual content of course entries). This fragmentation is one of the most commonly identified sources of inconsistency and delay in CC management.

International Relations Offices (IROs) and Erasmus+ coordinators occupy a particularly important position. They are daily users of CCs, both for managing incoming student applications and for advising outgoing students about host institution offerings. From both directions, they experience the consequences of CC inadequacies, outdated information, missing eligibility indicators, insufficient course detail, more directly than almost any other staff group.

2.1.2 Academic Staff

Academic staff (professors, lecturers and course convenors) are responsible for the underlying content of CC entries: course descriptions, learning outcomes, assessment methods, prerequisites, and syllabi. Their engagement with CC processes varies widely. In some institutions, academic staff are required to submit or validate course information through structured workflows; in others, the connection between teaching staff and CC management is informal or absent, resulting in entries that do not reflect current course reality. This gap between what is taught and what is described in the CC is a primary source of the accuracy problems documented throughout the research.

2.1.3 Quality Assurance and Accreditation Bodies

National quality assurance agencies, such as the Hellenic Authority for Higher Education (HAHE) in Greece, A3ES in Portugal, ANECA in Spain, and equivalent bodies in other partner

countries, exercise regulatory oversight over degree programmes and, by extension, over CC content. Accreditation requirements shape the minimum information that must be present in CCs and establish the timelines within which updates must be made. These external requirements create both a compliance floor (ensuring basic CC content exists) and a ceiling (insofar as compliance-oriented cultures may prioritise formal requirements over practical usability).

2.2 Student Stakeholders

2.2.1 Incoming Erasmus+ and Exchange Students

Incoming mobility students represent the most demanding user group for course catalogues. They interact with CCs under conditions of high uncertainty: they are unfamiliar with the host institution, its systems and its academic culture; they are often accessing CC information from abroad and in a second or third language; they are working to a tight timeline imposed by mobility application deadlines; and they are required to produce a formally binding Learning Agreement that will determine credit recognition upon return. Any inadequacy in the CC, such as incomplete information, outdated entries, missing eligibility flags, language barriers, poor navigation, directly impairs their ability to fulfil this process and can result in failed mobilities, stress, and academic disruption.

The XV ESN survey establishes clearly that availability of recognisable, matching courses is the single most important institutional pull factor in mobility destination selection, with an average importance score of 3.79 out of 5. This figure shows that CC quality outranks academic reputation (3.56) and language of instruction compatibility (3.61) as determinants of where students choose to go. The implication is direct: improving CC quality is not merely an administrative improvement. It is a lever for increasing mobility volume and institutional attractiveness.

2.2.2 Outgoing Students

Outgoing students from DACEM partner universities also interact with CCs, particularly those of potential host institutions, during the destination selection phase. They must assess whether a host institution offers courses that are recognisable by their home institution and align with their degree pathway. Their experience with other institutions' CCs is typically more critical than that of domestic users: they approach the CC without institutional familiarity, cannot rely on informal knowledge, and have no staff contact to resolve ambiguities immediately. The HEI staff survey documents high levels of difficulty experienced by staff advising outgoing students when relying on partner institutions' CCs.

2.2.3 Prospective and Non-Mobile Students

Prospective students, those deciding whether and where to study, consult CCs to understand the academic offer of institutions they are considering. For Erasmus+ purposes, the relevant decision is whether to participate in mobility at all and which partner institutions to select. Non-mobile students have received less research attention in this project, but the ESN surveys document that CCs also play a role in their understanding of their own institution's academic offer.

2.3 External Stakeholders

Beyond the institutional and student ecosystems, CCs serve additional audiences whose needs are often not considered in CC design. Employers and industry partners increasingly consult CCs to understand the competencies and qualifications of graduates from partner institutions, particularly in the context of European university alliances and transnational collaboration. Similarly, government bodies and accreditation agencies review CCs as part of programme monitoring and quality assurance. Researchers access CCs to identify collaboration opportunities, spot curriculum gaps, and understand teaching provision across the sector.

At the European level, the Erasmus Charter for Higher Education (ECHE) further reinforces the strategic importance of CCs. As a prerequisite for participation in the Erasmus+ programme, ECHE sets out clear expectations regarding transparency, accessibility, and the quality of information provided to students and partners. Institutions are required to publish up-to-date, accurate, and comprehensive course information in a publicly accessible format, typically in English, to support informed decision-making and fair mobility processes.

In this context, the Erasmus Without Paper (EWP) network and the Online Learning Agreement (OLA) platform represent an emerging class of digital stakeholders. As student mobility systems become progressively digitised, CCs must evolve from static, human-readable documents into interoperable, machine-readable resources. They need to provide structured data that can automatically populate learning agreements, ensure accurate course identification, support recognition processes, and enable seamless credit transfer across institutional and national boundaries. This requirement for technical interoperability represents a significant shift in the role and design of CCs, one that remains largely unaddressed in current practice, and calls for a rethinking of catalogues as integral components of a connected European digital education infrastructure.

3. National Course Catalogue Landscape (A2.1)

The CC Mapping report (Heidmann et al., 2024) conducted a systematic analysis of CC systems across eight partner countries. The analysis combined a documentary review of institutional CC platforms with case studies of generic, best-practice and problematic examples in each country. This section synthesises the most significant findings.

3.1 Country Profiles

France

French higher education institutions operate under the regulatory framework of the Ministry for Higher Education and Research (MESR), which grants universities significant autonomy in developing their own CC solutions. In practice, this has produced a two-tier landscape. A number of institutions have adopted **AMETYS Campus**, an open-source content management platform developed by the AMETYS company primarily for higher education and public authorities. Institutions using AMETYS include Université Savoie Mont-Blanc, Université de Toulouse, Université Paris Cité, Université de Nîmes, Université Paris Sud, Institut National Polytechnique de Toulouse, and Université de Poitiers; the Université d'Orléans is transitioning to the same platform.

A second group of French institutions maintain bespoke, custom-built IT solutions for their CCs. While these may be tailored to institutional needs, they typically lack the standardised structure required for effective cross-institutional comparison by mobility students. The Campus France platform, operated by the French agency for the promotion of higher education, nominally presents study programmes from French HEIs but was found to be non-functional at the time of analysis.

The qualitative and quantitative data consistently identify France as a relatively weak performer on CC quality indicators, particularly in English-language provision, course-level detail (rather than programme-level information), completeness, and ease of use for international students. The HEI staff survey places French institutions among the lowest on several satisfaction dimensions related to visiting students.

Greece

Greek universities produce CCs collaboratively within departments, with Erasmus+ students as the primary intended audience. Compliance with the Hellenic Authority for Higher Education (HAHE) ensures adherence to national quality standards, and regular coordination between faculty members and Erasmus+ participants is embedded in the CC update cycle.

The University of Thessaly, one of the DACEM partners, provides a representative example: its CC is generally regarded as adequate for basic course matching between partner institutions, but lacks interactivity, real-time updates, integration with schedules, and multimedia content.

The number of courses available to Erasmus+ students is a commonly identified limitation in Greek CCs, reflecting a broader challenge of departmental autonomy in determining eligibility for exchange students. Despite these limitations, Greek institutions perform reasonably on formal ECHE compliance indicators and on the ECTS-based structure of their catalogues.

Spain

Spain presents one of the most advanced and diverse CC landscapes among the partner countries. Institutions such as the University of Vigo (UVigo) and the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM) have developed sophisticated online systems that provide detailed information on course types, credit distribution, teaching methods, and languages of instruction. Quality assurance is maintained through compliance with ANECA (National Agency for Quality Assessment and Accreditation) standards. The Royal Decree 822/2021 and the LOSU Organic Law provide the regulatory framework.

Best-practice examples identified in Spain include the University of Granada's UGRcat platform, notable for its user-friendly search functionality and well-structured course information; the Universitat Oberta de Catalunya (UOC), whose CC platform was specifically redesigned and relaunched in 2023 with a student-centred approach; and the Universidad Pública de Navarra (UPNA). The centrally maintained RUCT registry provides a baseline of programme information for all Spanish institutions. Despite these strengths, persistent problems with scattered information across multiple platforms, inconsistent update schedules, and variable English-language provision are documented, particularly at the Erasmus+ coordinator level.

Portugal

Portugal's CC landscape benefits from a strong national regulatory framework, A3ES accreditation requirements, the DGES (Directorate-General for Higher Education) centralised course-assistant tool, and a relatively well-developed culture of ECTS documentation. Institutions such as the Polytechnic Institute of Porto (IPP), the University of Lisbon (ULisboa), the University of Minho (UMinho), the University of Porto (U.Porto), the University of Coimbra

(UC), and the University of Aveiro (UA) all maintain accessible, regularly updated CCs, often using the SIGARRA system.

The University of Coimbra is identified as a best-practice example for its comprehensive ECTS catalogue, which includes detailed programme and course information in both Portuguese and English. The Virtual Campus, the Portuguese DACEM partner, provides specific insights on the need to extend CC content beyond academic information to include student life, housing, cost of living, and campus logistics, particularly for incoming exchange students planning from abroad.

Slovenia

Slovenia is among the stronger performers among partner countries on formal CC compliance indicators. The ECHE-compliant publication schedule requires the official CC to be published by the end of March or early April, with updates only in exceptional cases. The AIPS (Academic Information System) allows students to select courses across faculties, with CCs available in both PDF and Excel formats on the institutional website for easy access and sorting.

All exchange courses at the University of Maribor, the Slovenian DACEM partner, are taught in English, providing a model for language provision. The HEI staff survey places Slovenia among the stronger performers on most CC quality indicators. However, qualitative research in Maribor identified reliance on PDF-based formats as a significant limitation for mobile access, underscoring that formal compliance and practical digital usability are distinct dimensions.

Hungary

Hungary operates a structured IT-driven approach to CC management, with defined workflows, standardised templates, enforced deadlines, and a centralised data repository. The key responsibilities in CC management include designing and managing process workflows and timelines, gathering course and programme information using predefined templates, standardising and validating data, integrating it into a central repository, and maintaining the software infrastructure.

Key platforms include the Neptun student information system, which is used at ELTE (Eötvös Loránd University) for mobility course listing; dedicated Erasmus+ pages at universities such as the Budapest University of Technology and Economics (BME/KTH), the Metropolitan Ervin Szabó Library Budapest, the University of Szeged, the University of Debrecen, Semmelweis University, and Corvinus University. A notable complication in the Hungarian context is the 'model change' of some public universities to foundation-based governance, which has

created uncertainty around Erasmus+ participation and, in some cases, affected CC accessibility and the mobility offer.

Estonia

Estonia's CC landscape is characterised by relatively high institutional maturity. The ÕIS2 system at Tallinn University provides an integrated platform for course catalogue management and student registration, with strict timeline compliance: autumn semester exchange courses are published by the end of March for student selection beginning April 1, and spring semester courses by the end of September for selection beginning October 1. All courses must include information in both Estonian and English, covering title, assessment form, aims, description, and learning outcomes.

TalTech (Tallinn University of Technology) and the University of Tartu also maintain comprehensive CC systems, though the University of Tartu, while having a public ÕIS2 catalogue, lacks a distinct section for incoming exchange courses on its main homepage, which can create navigation difficulties for international students. Estonia is consistently identified as one of the stronger performers in the HEI staff survey. Tallinn University's CC system is specifically praised by focus group participants from other partner countries as a model of clarity and accessibility.

Czechia

Czech HEIs, including Charles University and Masaryk University, maintain comprehensive online CC systems with detailed information on programme offerings, credit distribution, and academic policies. Quality assurance oversight by national agencies ensures regulatory compliance. However, the qualitative research at Charles University identified several specific gaps: inadequate signalling of Erasmus+ course eligibility; filtering functionality organised by faculty rather than by study field, making cross-disciplinary navigation difficult; and inconsistency in the depth of English-language course descriptions. Czechia performs moderately in the HEI staff survey, with stronger scores on structural indicators than on usability and language accessibility.

3.2 Common Operational Requirements Across Countries

Despite the diversity of national contexts and CC systems, the mapping identified a set of operational requirements that are common across all eight countries. These represent the baseline infrastructure for any functioning CC system:

- **Institutional autonomy in content management:** In all countries studied, HEIs retain significant autonomy in scientific and pedagogical domains, allowing them to develop CC content according to their own academic structures. This autonomy is a source of both flexibility and inconsistency.
- **Regulatory compliance:** Institutions must comply with national accreditation requirements and international frameworks (ECTS, ECHE), which establish minimum content standards and publication timelines.
- **Quality assurance integration:** National QA agencies in each country exercise oversight over programme quality, which impacts CC content and structure. The specific requirements vary by country but generally include periodic programme review and accreditation.
- **Technological infrastructure:** All countries rely on online platforms for CC management, though the sophistication, interoperability, and user-friendliness of these platforms vary enormously, from custom-built integrated systems (ÕIS2 in Estonia, Neptun in Hungary) to simple web-based document hosting.

Beyond these baseline requirements, the mapping identified several more advanced operational elements that distinguish high-performing CC systems from those that merely meet minimum standards:

- **Workflow governance:** In the most mature CC systems (notably Hungary and Estonia), the production of CC content is managed through formally specified workflows with defined roles, deadlines and escalation processes. Academic departments are required to submit content through standardised templates, and a central office is responsible for validation, integration and publication. In less mature systems, content production depends on informal conventions and individual goodwill, resulting in greater variability and less reliable update cycles.
- **Stakeholder co-production:** Several institutions have moved toward models in which Erasmus+ coordinators, academic staff and student representatives are actively involved in the design and review of CC content. In Greece, for example, regular coordination meetings between faculty members and Erasmus+ participants are embedded in the CC update cycle. In Slovenia, feedback from exchange students is systematically collected and used to inform CC improvements. These co-production models tend to produce CC content that is better aligned with students' actual needs.
- **Integration with the mobility calendar:** Effective CC systems are explicitly designed around the mobility calendar, the sequence of deadlines that governs when students apply, when they receive offers, when they draft Learning Agreements, and when they finalise their course selection. Slovenia's requirement to publish the CC by the end of

March or early April, and Estonia's specific timelines for autumn (end of March) and spring (end of September) course list updates, reflect this calendar alignment. In countries where no such integration exists, CC publication is driven by internal academic planning cycles that may not correspond to mobility timelines at all.

- **Use of structured use cases:** The A2.1 mapping documented specific use cases, concrete scenarios in which different stakeholders interact with the CC, that help illustrate the operational requirements in practice. Key use cases include: an incoming exchange student identifying courses for Learning Agreement preparation; an Erasmus+ coordinator using the CC to verify course availability and create a curated list for incoming students; an outgoing student browsing partner institution CCs to compare destinations; and an academic department head reviewing the CC to identify gaps or redundancies in the programme offering.

3.3 Summary of Good Practice Examples

The A2.1 mapping identified several exemplary CC models that stand out for their combination of comprehensive content, user-friendly design, technical sophistication, and effective institutional integration. These examples were further reinforced by the HEI staff survey's open comments section, where respondents named specific external CCs they found particularly useful. Table 2 summarises the key good-practice examples identified across the research.

Table 2: Summary of Good Practices

Institution	Platform / System	Key Strengths Identified
University of Granada (ES)	UGRcat platform	User-friendly search, clear ECTS information, accessible course-level detail
Universitat Oberta de Catalunya (ES)	Dedicated CC platform (relaunched 2023)	Student-centred design, comprehensive course-level information, full online accessibility
University of Coimbra (PT)	ECTS catalogue	Bilingual (PT/EN) programme and course documentation, comprehensive and well-structured
Tallinn University (EE)	ÕIS2 integrated system	Bilingual CC and registration platform, strict timeline compliance, praised by partner institutions
University of Maribor (SI)	AIPS + web publication	Full English provision for exchange courses, early publication, multi-format access
University of Copenhagen (DK)*	kurser.ku.dk	Cited by staff survey respondents: clarity, completeness, easy LA preparation

Ghent University (BE)*	ugent.be/en/programmes	Cited by staff survey respondents: strong structure, ECTS alignment, accessible
Politecnico di Milano (IT)*	polimi.it/en/education	Cited by staff survey respondents: clear course codes, well-organised international section
TU Wien (AT)*	TISS platform	Cited by staff survey respondents: comprehensive, searchable, mobility-ready
Lodz University of Technology (PL)*	ECTS label web	Cited by staff survey respondents: clarity on credits, content and level

* External institutions cited by HEI staff survey respondents, not DACEM partners.

Analysis of these good-practice examples reveals a set of common characteristics that distinguish high-performing CCs from the average:

- First, all of the top-performing systems are genuinely course-level rather than only programme-level: they provide detailed information about individual courses, not merely lists of modules within a degree structure.
- Second, all provide comprehensive English-language content, not just translated titles but full descriptions, learning outcomes and assessment information.
- Third, all feature meaningful search and filtering functionality that allows students to narrow results by language, level, field and semester without having to manually browse entire catalogues.
- Fourth, all are published and updated in alignment with mobility application timelines, giving students reliable information when they need it most.
- Fifth, all provide stable, persistent URLs for individual courses and programmes, enabling direct linking from Learning Agreements and institutional websites.

The common thread running through these best practices is intentionality: the institutions and systems that perform best have explicitly designed their CCs with mobility students as a primary audience, rather than treating international accessibility as an add-on to a system built for domestic use. This design intention shapes every dimension of the CC, from the decision to provide full English-language content, to the choice of filtering dimensions, to the publication timeline, to the structure of course descriptions. The DACEM project's technical model work should draw heavily on the design principles demonstrated by these exemplary cases.

4. Qualitative Research Findings (A2.2)

The Focus Groups and Interviews Final Report (Jesmin et al., 2024) presents the findings of qualitative research conducted with 230 participants across the nine DACEM partner universities between May and October 2024. The research involved structured interviews with Erasmus+ coordinators and institutional staff responsible for CC management, as well as focus group discussions with international and incoming exchange students. The data collection period was extended into the autumn 2024 semester due to scheduling challenges over the summer, ensuring adequate representation from all partner institutions.

4.1 Cross-Partner Thematic Findings

4.1.1 Challenges with Course Catalogues

The most consistently identified challenge across all nine partner institutions is the lack of up-to-date and accurate information in CCs. Students and staff frequently encounter outdated course descriptions, some reflecting curricula from previous years, as well as listings of courses that are not actually offered in the upcoming semester. This problem is compounded by a fundamental timing mismatch: mobility application deadlines typically fall months before the academic year for which students are selecting courses, meaning that the CC information students rely on is inherently prospective. When this information subsequently changes, as it frequently does, students must amend their LAs, creating an administrative burden for themselves, their home institutions, and their host institutions.

The limited level of detail in course descriptions was identified as a second major challenge. Students and coordinators consistently reported the absence of critical information: course objectives and learning outcomes; assessment methods (written vs oral exams, continuous assessment, project-based assessment); grading criteria; contact hours and workload breakdown; prerequisite knowledge requirements; and bibliographic resources. This absence forces students to seek supplementary information through direct contact with academic staff or other students, a time-consuming process that is particularly difficult for students planning their mobility from abroad.

Structural inconsistencies across institutions compound the navigation challenge. Different institutions categorise courses by faculty, study field, degree level, or some combination of these; use different terminology for equivalent concepts; and present information in different formats and layouts. For students comparing course offerings across multiple potential host institutions, these inconsistencies create significant cognitive load and increase the risk of mismatched selections.

The absence of clear indicators indicating whether courses are open or not to Erasmus+ students was flagged as a specific and practically significant problem. Many courses in a CC are restricted to degree-enrolled students or to students at a specific level; without clear eligibility signposting, exchange students must contact the institution or the relevant faculty to determine their eligibility, adding friction and uncertainty to an already complex process.

Finally, search and filtering functionality was widely criticised as inadequate. Many CC platforms offer only basic search tools, often limited to keyword search within course titles, without the ability to filter by language of instruction, study level, academic field, semester availability, ECTS credits, or Erasmus+ eligibility. This limitation forces students to manually scan large catalogue sections, dramatically increasing the time required to identify suitable courses and increasing the risk of overlooking relevant options.

4.1.2 Positive Aspects and Functional Features

Despite the breadth of challenges identified, the qualitative research also documented a range of features that participants valued when they were available. When present, advanced search and filtering functionality was consistently praised as transformative for usability. Systems that allow filtering by language of instruction, study level, and semester availability dramatically reduce the time required to identify suitable courses. Direct links from CC entries to faculty pages, detailed syllabi, or course registration platforms were valued for enabling seamless progression from course discovery to enrolment.

The integration of interactive and multimedia content was noted as a positive trend. Virtual campus tours, video course previews, professor profile pages, and student testimonials were identified as particularly valuable for incoming international students who have had no prior contact with the institution. These elements help reduce the uncertainty associated with choosing courses at an unfamiliar institution in an unfamiliar country.

Multi-lingual support, particularly full English-language provision, was consistently identified as a key enabler of accessibility for mobility students. Institutions providing comprehensive English-language CC content were regarded as significantly more welcoming and accessible than those providing only partial translations or national-language-only content. Several participants noted that the quality of English-language provision was a significant factor in their perception of an institution's commitment to international students.

Integration of CCs with broader administrative systems, such as LA platforms, enrolment tools, and institutional student information systems, was valued for reducing the fragmentation of the mobility process. Where students could move seamlessly from course discovery to agreement preparation to registration within a single platform, or with minimal platform switching, their experience was significantly more positive.

4.1.3 Recommendations Emerging from Qualitative Research

Across all nine institutions, a consistent set of recommendations emerged. CCs should prioritise comprehensive, accurate and up-to-date information, with clear update protocols and meaningful timestamps. Course descriptions should include all information required to make an informed decision: prerequisites, assessment methods, schedules, ECTS credits, language of instruction, and clear Erasmus+ eligibility status. A standardised cross-institutional structure would substantially reduce the navigation burden for mobility students. Search and filtering functionality must be substantially improved. Mobile access is a baseline expectation, not a premium feature. Integration with EWP and OLA tools should be a design requirement, not an afterthought.

4.2 Institution-by-Institution Findings

Tallinn University (Estonia)

Staff and students at Tallinn University reported significant navigation difficulties, particularly with the CCs of Southern European partner institutions, which were characterised as disorganised, fragmented across multiple platforms, and outdated. Course codes, semester dates, and even course availability were frequently incorrect in partner CCs, creating confusion during course selection. Tallinn University's own ÖIS2-based CC was generally praised for its clarity and organisation.

Key recommendations from Tallinn University participants: implementation of mobile-responsive CC design as a standard requirement; advanced filtering functionality including filtering by academic year and course availability status; inclusion of multimedia content (course preview videos, student testimonials, professor introductions); clear visual differentiation between undergraduate and graduate courses; automated audit and reminder systems to maintain information currency; and better integration between CC information and the post-application access to course details.

University of Thessaly (Greece)

The University of Thessaly's CC was generally regarded as satisfactory by students, academic coordinators and Erasmus+ office professionals, despite its limited interactivity. The primary concern was the limited range of courses available to exchange students. Participants identified a strong need for a centralised approach to CC management, ensuring easy access to comprehensive course descriptions for the full institutional offering rather than a restricted Erasmus+ subset.

Recommended content improvements: detailed course objectives, schedules, assessment formats, industry connections, mentorship opportunities, and instructor profiles; real-time

updates to lecture times and project deadlines; videos about course activities and student feedback; clear ECTS recognition guidance. Functionality improvements: enhanced search, interactivity allowing filtering by course characteristics and specialisations, accessibility for students with disabilities, and a mobile-friendly interface. The CC was also identified as a potential tool for Erasmus+ information days and other student support activities.

University of Vigo (Spain)

The University of Vigo's qualitative research revealed two major categories of concern: outdated and inaccurate information, including malfunctioning search features and scattered information across multiple platforms; and a widespread recognition that the CC is significantly under-utilised relative to its potential. Participants proposed a richer vision for the CC's role: as a tool for Erasmus coordinators in preparing bilateral agreements and identifying mobility destinations; as a resource for teacher mobility, enabling staff to identify courses and academic colleagues at partner institutions; as a vehicle for identifying gaps in institutional programmes; and as a support tool for universities developing programmes within European University Alliances.

Specific information gaps identified: campus and location details (particularly important for multi-city universities); grading system comparison between countries; information about recognition history (past successful credit transfer cases); student life information, including housing, costs, transport and cultural events; and direct contacts for Erasmus coordinators with the opportunity to connect with past and current students. Non-functional priorities: information harmonisation across institutions, mobile and web accessibility, regular transparent updates with validity dates, and avoidance of duplicated information across platforms.

University of Orleans (France)

The qualitative research at Orleans identified particularly acute CC deficiencies. The existing search engine did not support effective keyword search and lacked filters for geographic location, language of instruction, and examination periods. The catalogue was limited to degree programme information rather than individual course details, missing ECTS credits and syllabi. Some content relied on external websites that were frequently outdated. The separation of administrative and pedagogical registration processes added complexity and confusion.

The practical consequences documented at Orleans include students spending excessive time searching multiple platforms or contacting teaching staff directly, and in some cases, mobility opportunities being cancelled due to inaccessible or inaccurate CC information. Future CC features recommended by Orleans participants: sophisticated search with

geographic, language, and examination period filters; detailed syllabi and ECTS information; promotional videos and visual aids; a 'funnel model' for progressive access to specific course details; mobile optimisation; interoperability with institutional IT systems; support for students with specific needs; and potentially interactive display screens in faculty buildings for on-site browsing.

European University Foundation (EUF)

The EUF, as a European-level stakeholder, emphasised the need to transform the CC into a genuine 'one-stop shop' for all course-related information for mobility students. This vision encompasses not only comprehensive academic course information but also all the contextual information a student needs to make an informed mobility decision and to prepare effectively for their stay. Required information fields identified by EUF: standardised course descriptions enabling cross-institutional comparison; reading materials allowing home institution curriculum compatibility assessment; assessment methods including exam dates; course schedule and classroom location; clear Erasmus+ acceptance status; teacher name and contact details; application process and deadlines; and language of instruction.

Non-functional requirements prioritised by EUF: regularly updated information with synchronisation to mobility calendars; harmonisation of CC formats across European HEIs; supporting media content, including video tutorials; and mobile accessibility. Functional features: powerful, intuitive search, and connection to university registry systems enabling real-time course availability data.

Charles University (Czechia)

Charles University's focus group identified a range of specific improvements required to align CCs with the ECTS Users' Guide recommendations. Participants requested clear Erasmus+ eligibility indicators for each course; study-field-based filtering (rather than faculty-based filtering, which varies so much between institutions as to be confusing for outsiders); detailed guidelines for Erasmus+ students on how to navigate the CC and select appropriate courses; clear and reliable update processes with definitive timelines; links to individual university websites for more detailed information; and support for interdisciplinary course selection across faculties.

Charles University participants specified a detailed list of required course data fields: course title; study field; provider (faculty/department); study cycle (Bachelor, Master, PhD); ECTS credits; teacher name and contact; semester; prerequisites/corequisites; registration period and process; available places; detailed course description (content, goals, expected skills); comprehensive syllabus; mandatory and recommended literature; attestation type (exam format); language of instruction; attestation conditions; seminar/lecture balance; student

feedback from previous participants; and guidance on using the CC. Functional requirements: drop-down navigation to prevent information overload; system resilience for peak traffic periods; and pre-application access to full and current CC content.

Virtual Campus, Portugal

The Virtual Campus qualitative findings placed particular emphasis on practical decision-making information that extends beyond the academic course content. Participants highlighted the need for detailed campus and programme location descriptions, including maps, transport options, parking and local amenities, particularly important for multi-campus or multi-city universities. Transparent credit transfer information, including historical recognition data showing successful past transfers, was identified as highly valuable for reducing students' anxiety about recognition outcomes. Clear grading scale equivalence charts were recommended to help students understand how their international grades will be interpreted at home.

Beyond academic content, Virtual Campus participants advocated for student life and services information: housing options and availability, cultural activities, daily living costs, and a calendar of local events. Student profiles and testimonials from past and current exchange participants were proposed as mechanisms for peer-informed decision-making and to foster a sense of community. Erasmus coordinator contact details should be prominently available throughout the CC. Non-functional priorities: harmonisation and standardisation; accurate and updatable information with user-reporting mechanisms; full mobile and assistive technology compatibility; and rich multimedia content, including virtual tours and interactive maps.

University of Maribor (Slovenia)

University of Maribor participants expressed the strongest preferences around digital design and technical integration. The reliance on PDF-format CCs was identified as a critical limitation for mobile access and for students with specific accessibility needs. The preferred CC would offer a simple, user-friendly interface with advanced filtering, interactive previews (videos, photos), personalised course recommendations, and customisable personal dashboards. Multi-lingual support was emphasised to serve the international audience effectively.

Non-functional requirements at Maribor: constant, real-time updating of course availability, enrolment conditions and curriculum changes; unique stable links to individual courses and programmes for easy sharing; and clear, consistent terminology throughout. Integration priorities: connection to EWP and OLA platforms to streamline enrolment; AI-driven chatbots to reduce communication burden on coordinators; and direct course registration capability

from within the CC interface. Enhanced search and filtering: by course type, instructor, schedule, and location; with department information for each course. Both students and coordinators at Maribor emphasised that simplifying the interface and integrating modern notification features would substantially improve the experience for Erasmus+ students.

5. Survey Findings (A2.3)

The Surveys on Course Catalogues Report (ESN / University of Vigo, 2025) presents the quantitative evidence base assembled from four survey instruments. This section summarises the key findings across three analytical perspectives: the student perspective before departure, during, and after mobility, and the HEI staff perspective.

5.1 Large-Scale ESN Student Surveys

5.1.1 Survey Design and Reach

The XV ESN survey was conducted online between 18 May and 31 July 2023, disseminated through ESN's network of local and national sections, National Agencies, universities and student organisations. From the full dataset (N=22,775), the analysis focused on Erasmus+ participants (N=17,855), excluding non-mobile students (N=3,064) and international full-degree students (N=1,856). The survey contained 145 questions; 14 were selected for this analysis as directly relevant to CC quality and mobility experiences.

The XVI ESN survey was conducted between 12 May and 31 August 2025, following the same dissemination structure. The full sample totalled N=19,704, of whom N=6,975 Erasmus+ participants were analysed for this report. The XVI survey contained 167 questions across different respondent categories: the analysis selected questions relating to the DACEM project scope, including motivation for mobility, factors in destination choice, pre-departure support satisfaction, teaching methodologies, and CC-specific dimensions.

5.1.2 Pre-Departure: Pull Factors and the Role of Course Catalogues

A central finding of the XV ESN survey is that course-related factors dominate students' choice of mobility destination. When asked to rate the importance of various pull factors on a 5-point Likert scale, students assigned the highest institutional pull factor score to the availability of matching courses that could be recognised by their home institutions (mean = 3.79, SD = 1.26). This result underlines the strategic importance of CC quality: institutions with clearer, more comprehensive, and more reliable CCs are more directly attractive as mobility destinations.

Other significant pull factors include the affordability of the host city (M=3.83, SD=1.04, the highest single factor, reflecting practical considerations that the ECTS Users' Guide recommends should be addressed within the CC), language compatibility (M=3.61, SD=1.38), and academic reputation (M=3.56, SD=1.10). The XVI ESN survey reinforces these findings: course recognition, connections to career paths, and learning methodologies rank among the most important factors for mobility decisions, confirming that the content and

quality of course information communicated through CCs have direct consequences for institutional attractiveness.

5.1.3 Pre-Departure Support Satisfaction

The XV ESN survey assessed student satisfaction with the range of support services provided by home institutions before departure, using a 5-point Likert scale. Overall, students express positive satisfaction with core administrative and informational processes. Key positive ratings include support in preparing the Learning Agreement (M=3.82, SD=1.14), information and support on ECTS and study recognition (M=3.74, SD=1.16), and information about mobility opportunities and financial aid.

Satisfaction is more nuanced in areas where support quality depends on CC accuracy: information about courses offered by potential host universities elicits a moderately positive response, with a substantial neutral segment, reflecting the inherent uncertainty students face when relying on CC information that may not accurately reflect what they will find upon arrival. Support for students with fewer opportunities or special needs generates very high 'not applicable' response rates alongside comparatively low satisfaction among those who engage with it, indicating a structural inclusion gap in the current mobility support system.

The XVI ESN survey shows that financial support information, application process guidance, programme offers, and host university course information are among the most highly valued pre-departure informational services. This confirms that the CC, as the primary vehicle for communicating course-level information, sits at the heart of students' most critical informational need.

5.1.4 Post-Return: The Credit Recognition Gap

The most striking quantitative finding of the large-scale surveys concerns the relationship between CC quality and credit recognition outcomes. The XV ESN survey documents that, on average, students initially include 33 ECTS credits in their Learning Agreements. Upon arrival, they must adjust approximately 14 ECTS, representing a revision rate of over 40% by credit volume. This adjustment is largely driven by discrepancies between the course information in the CC and the actual courses available upon arrival. Ultimately, students complete approximately 30 ECTS during their mobility and have 28 ECTS recognised by their home institution, leaving a 2-credit shortfall that reflects the ongoing imperfection of recognition processes.

The headline figure is 42% of Erasmus+ students having to alter their course plans during their exchange. While a portion of this may reflect legitimate academic reasons, the research makes clear that a significant portion stems directly from CC inaccuracy: cancelled courses,

changed timetables, incorrect prerequisite information, or courses listed as open to exchange students that are, in practice, unavailable. This figure represents both a quality failure and an equity issue: students who lack the flexibility, language skills, or support network to manage last-minute plan changes are disproportionately disadvantaged.

At the extreme, 2.6% of survey respondents reported that none of their credits was recognised upon return. While small in proportion, this represents thousands of students across the Erasmus+ programme each year, for whom the mobility experience resulted in complete academic failure from a credit perspective. Contributing factors include inflexibility in degree structures, faculty members' individual interpretations of recognition decisions, trust issues between partner universities, and the absence of comprehensive, reliable CC information that could have enabled better-matched course selections from the outset.

Satisfaction with credit recognition support is relatively high ($M=3.85$, $SD=1.17$), reflecting that most students do eventually see their credits recognised, even after adjustment. However, satisfaction drops significantly when attention turns to post-mobility employability support ($M=3.14$, $SD=1.27$), and reintegration activity satisfaction is notably weak ($M=2.66$, $SD=1.40$). This suggests that CCs, if extended to articulate learning outcomes, skills acquired, and competency profiles, could add value not only in the pre-departure planning phase but also in post-return recognition of the professional value of the mobility experience.

5.1.5 ECHE Compliance and Student Perception

The XV ESN survey assessed student perceptions of how well host institutions fulfil their ECHE obligations across a range of service dimensions. CC accessibility and completeness at host institutions scores 3.71 ($SD=1.14$), reasonable but below the highest-rated ECHE dimension, and notably below the score for 'Learning Agreement signed by all parties with clear descriptions of all activities' ($M=3.95$, $SD=1.02$). This latter finding is important: students rate LA clarity highly precisely because it depends on CC accuracy; LA preparation is the downstream process for which CC quality is most immediately consequential.

Fully automatic recognition of learning outcomes scores 3.84 ($SD=1.08$), indicating room for improvement despite relatively strong performance on formal recognition indicators. Information on credit transfer and grade conversion procedures receives the lowest score in this cluster at 3.57 ($SD=1.12$), directly reflecting the inadequacy of this information in many CCs. Regarding the Erasmus Student Charter, 20.7% of students (approximately 3,053 of 14,751 respondents) were never informed of their rights, highlighting significant gaps in the broader information provision ecosystem surrounding mobility, of which the CC is a central component.

5.2 Short-Scale DACEM Bridging Survey (N=195)

The 2024 DACEM bridging survey, distributed to students from DACEM partner institutions in October 2024, provides localised validation of the patterns seen in the large-scale ESN surveys. The survey's 55 questions span the full mobility cycle, pre-departure, during mobility, and post-return, with specific attention to CC-related experiences.

Home institution support ratings confirm the patterns observed in the ESN surveys: strong positive evaluations for funding information, LA guidance, and ECTS/recognition support; more mixed evaluations for information about courses at the host institution and for support with language preparation and special needs. The survey identifies a particularly strong 'not applicable' pattern for inclusion-related support services, reinforcing the finding that standard mobility support systems are built around an assumed 'standard student profile' that may not reflect the diversity of the actual participant population.

On the host institution's CC specifically, the bridging survey finds strong satisfaction with formal/technical criteria (ECTS-based structure, online publication, early availability), but more critical assessments of reliability (up-to-date information and stability), language accessibility, and practical usability. The survey's 'problems experienced during mobility' module documents that course-related difficulties, particularly enrolment procedures and scheduling, are the most commonly reported challenges, followed by assessment and grading system discrepancies. These patterns directly implicate CC accuracy and completeness as causal factors.

5.3 HEI Staff Survey

5.3.1 Survey Design

The HEI staff survey was conducted online between February and December 2025, targeting academic and administrative staff directly involved in managing incoming and outgoing mobility students. The survey combined closed-ended Likert-scale questions with open-ended qualitative responses, covering two main analytical perspectives: staff assessments of their own institution's CC, and staff assessments of partner institutions' CCs as experienced in their daily mobility management work. The dataset includes contributions from institutions across multiple European countries, providing a cross-national view of CC quality from the staff perspective.

5.3.2 Views on Own Institution's CC

Staff assessments of their own CCs reveal a consistent pattern: relatively high confidence in formal and structural dimensions (ECTS alignment, online publication, basic consistency) combined with lower satisfaction when CCs are evaluated as practical tools for visiting

students. Most country averages fall between 2.5 and 4 on the 5-point scale, confirming a landscape of 'adequate but not excellent, a finding that aligns closely with the qualitative research.

Poland and Slovenia emerge as the strongest performers, with consistently high scores across multiple dimensions. The Czech Republic and Estonia also perform well on structural indicators, though they score slightly lower on ease of use. France scores consistently lowest, particularly on qualitative dimensions such as completeness, ease of use, and language accessibility. Germany, Italy, Greece, Portugal and Spain occupy intermediate positions, with partial effectiveness and internal inconsistencies.

Satisfaction with one's own CC as a tool for visiting students drops noticeably relative to general quality assessments. The weakest areas are information about key contact persons for Learning Agreement preparation (insufficient across most countries); information about course subjects with sufficient depth and clarity for visiting students; and information about resources and services available to visiting students (accommodation, transport, living costs). The strongest area is information on ECTS, grade transfer and recognition, reflecting the success of Bologna-era standardisation in this domain.

Open-ended responses reveal that quantitative satisfaction ratings often reflect conditional adequacy rather than genuine quality. Respondents who rated their CC positively in closed questions simultaneously described it as 'basic', 'incomplete', or 'primarily designed for domestic students'. The language barrier emerges as a structural concern even in otherwise well-rated systems: institutions describe their CC as reliable and well-structured but acknowledge it is 'mainly in the national language' or 'not fully available in English'. Institutional fragmentation is explicitly named as a limiting factor: many respondents clarify that no single, unified CC exists at their institution, and faculties maintain separate versions with different update schedules, structures and language policies.

5.3.3 Institutional Awareness of CC Problems

The survey asked staff to indicate which specific problems they had experienced with their own institution's CC when working with incoming students. The results reveal selective and uneven problem awareness. The most widely recognised problems relate to course information (descriptions, enrolment procedures, scheduling), acknowledged by the majority of respondents in several countries. Assessment and grading regulation issues are also widely recognised. Access to resources and academic facilities generates moderate awareness. Social integration difficulties receive the least acknowledgement, likely because they fall outside what staff associate with CC responsibilities.

A critical insight is that awareness of problems does not translate automatically into resolution. Many of the most significant CC issues, unstable course information, late updates, and inadequate English provision are well known to institutional staff. The remaining challenge is systemic: translating awareness into redesign. This requires not only institutional willingness but also technical capacity, appropriate governance structures, and in many cases external support or standardised frameworks.

5.3.4 Views on Other Institutions' CCs

Staff assessments of partner institutions' CCs are uniformly more critical than self-assessments, reflecting an asymmetry of familiarity that is itself a significant finding. From the outside, partner CCs are perceived as partially transparent but insufficiently reliable: ECTS alignment is generally assumed (the most widely agreed feature), but timeliness, language accessibility, completeness and ease of use all receive substantially lower ratings than for respondents' own institutions.

The most frequently experienced problems with other institutions' CCs are: unclear or incomplete course subject information (very high in Czech Republic, Estonia, Italy, Poland and Slovenia, in some cases reported by virtually all respondents); assessment and examination regulation opacity (high in Italy, France, Germany and Spain); access to resources and facilities information (moderate across multiple countries); and mobility documentation difficulties, LA and Grant Agreement problems, stemming from unstable or ambiguous course information (Italy, France, Germany, Spain).

Open-ended responses from this section of the survey vividly illustrate the practical consequences of poor external CCs. Respondents describe outdated catalogues discovered during LA preparation; late publication rendering CC content useless for the application period; courses cancelled after LA approval; language of instruction incorrectly stated in the CC; and students having to make multiple LA amendments due to unreliable information. These are described not as isolated incidents but as recurring, predictable challenges that have become part of the standard coordination workflow, a normalisation of dysfunction that points to the need for systemic rather than individual institutional solutions.

5.4 Summary of Survey Key Metrics

The table below consolidates the most significant quantitative metrics emerging from the A2.3 survey work. These figures provide a statistical foundation for the policy and institutional recommendations in Section 7 and for the cross-cutting analysis in Section 6.

Table 3: Key survey metrics

Metric	Value	Source
Importance of recognisable course availability (pull factor)	3.79/5	XV ESN survey, N=14,483
Academic reputation as pull factor	3.56/5	XV ESN survey, N=14,483
Language of instruction as pull factor	3.61/5	XV ESN survey, N=14,483
Host city affordability as pull factor	3.83/5	XV ESN survey, N=14,483
Satisfaction: LA preparation support (home institution)	3.82/5	XV ESN survey, N=14,491
Satisfaction: ECTS and recognition support (home institution)	3.74/5	XV ESN survey, N=14,491
Average ECTS in initial Learning Agreement	~33 ECTS	XV ESN survey, N=6,620
Average ECTS adjusted upon arrival at host institution	~14 ECTS	XV ESN survey, N=6,620
Students who had to alter course plans during mobility	42%	XV ESN survey, N=6,620
Average ECTS completed during mobility	~30 ECTS	XV ESN survey, N=6,620
Average ECTS recognised by home institution after return	~28 ECTS	XV ESN survey, N=6,620
Students reporting zero credit recognition	2.6%	XV ESN survey, N=6,620
Satisfaction: credit recognition support (home institution)	3.85/5	XV ESN survey, N=20,532
CC accessibility and completeness at host institutions	3.71/5	XV ESN survey (ECHE compliance)
LA signed with clear descriptions, most positively rated ECHE item	3.95/5	XV ESN survey (ECHE compliance)
Full automatic recognition of learning outcomes	3.84/5	XV ESN survey (ECHE compliance)
Information on credit transfer and grade conversion	3.57/5	XV ESN survey (ECHE compliance)
Satisfaction: linking exchange to employment	3.14/5	XV ESN survey, N=17,855
Satisfaction: reintegration activities	2.66/5	XV ESN survey, N=17,855
Students never informed of Erasmus Student Charter	20.7%	XV ESN survey, N=14,751
Proportion reaching students at first awareness of Erasmus	38%	XV ESN survey, N=14,751

6. Cross-Cutting Analytical Synthesis

When the findings of all three WP2 activity reports are triangulated, five cross-cutting analytical themes emerge. These themes represent the most structurally important insights from the evidence base, those that appear consistently across all three research methods and across all eight partner countries. Each theme has direct implications for the recommendations in Section 7.

6.1. Theme 1: The Compliance–Usability Gap

The most fundamental cross-cutting finding of the WP2 research is the gap between formal compliance and practical usability. CCs across Europe have largely met the baseline requirements established by the Bologna Process and the ECHE: they are generally ECTS-based, published online, and structured according to recognisable academic categories. These formal attributes are confirmed by the HEI staff survey, which shows that compliance-oriented dimensions consistently receive the highest scores, and by the A2.1 mapping, which identifies functional CC systems in all eight partner countries.

However, formal compliance does not translate into practical usability for the key user group: mobility students navigating an unfamiliar system from a distance, under time pressure, in a second language. The qualitative research at all nine partner institutions documents widespread frustration with CCs that are technically available but difficult to navigate, incomplete in their course-level detail, unreliable in their currency, and poorly adapted to the specific needs of Erasmus+ students. The quantitative surveys confirm this at scale: CC accessibility and completeness at host institutions scores only 3.71/5 in the XV ESN survey, and the 42% Learning Agreement amendment rate demonstrates that compliance-level CCs systematically fail to support effective pre-departure planning.

The central implication of this theme is that the question for policy and institutional practice is no longer 'Do CCs exist?' but 'Are CCs genuinely useful for mobility?' The challenge has shifted from formal compliance to mobility readiness. This reframing has significant implications for how ECHE monitoring is conducted and for the standards applied in future Erasmus+ framework negotiations.

6.2. Theme 2: Temporal Instability and Trust Erosion

Across all three research activities, the timing and stability of CC information emerge as a critical failure point. The fundamental challenge is structural: mobility application deadlines fall months before the academic year for which students are selecting courses. This means that the CC information students rely on during the application phase is inherently

provisional, a snapshot of planned course provision that is subject to change before and after the student arrives.

The research documents multiple dimensions of temporal instability: CCs updated after mobility application deadlines, making the information students relied on outdated; courses listed as available that are subsequently cancelled or restructured; timetable information published only after Learning Agreements are finalised; and seasonal update cycles driven by accreditation requirements rather than mobility calendars. These patterns are documented in the A2.1 mapping across multiple countries, confirmed qualitatively at all nine partner institutions, and quantified in the survey data: 42% of students alter their course plans upon arrival, adjusting on average 14 ECTS credits.

The cumulative effect of repeated temporal instability is erosion of trust. When students and coordinators learn from experience that CC information cannot be relied upon, they develop workarounds, direct contact with academic departments, reliance on personal networks, and deferral of LA completion until the last possible moment. These workarounds are individually rational but collectively dysfunctional: they increase administrative burden, discriminate against students who lack the language skills or contacts to navigate informally, and perpetuate a culture in which CC improvement is deprioritised because staff assume students will find another way.

Rebuilding trust in CC information requires not only more accurate content but also visible accountability mechanisms: timestamps, published update schedules, user-reporting tools for flagging outdated content, and, where possible, freeze periods that protect LA preparation by preventing late course changes from cascading into agreement instability.

6.3. Theme 3: Language as a Structural Barrier

Multilingual provision, particularly in English, is identified as inadequate across all three research activities and in all eight partner countries. This is not a marginal or secondary concern: for incoming international students, the language in which a CC is published is often the first factor in determining whether it is usable at all. A CC that provides comprehensive, accurate, and well-structured content in a national language only is, from the perspective of most incoming Erasmus+ students, effectively a closed system.

The research documents multiple dimensions of the language problem. At the most basic level, many institutions provide CC content only in their national language, with no English translation. More subtly, some institutions provide partial translations, course titles and credit values in English, but descriptions and learning outcomes only in the national language, which gives the appearance of accessibility while withholding the substantive content

students need to make informed decisions. At the most problematic level, some institutions list courses as 'English-taught' in their CC but provide course descriptions only in the national language or impose additional language requirements that become apparent only upon arrival.

The HEI staff survey confirms that language accessibility consistently receives among the lowest satisfaction ratings, even in countries whose CCs perform well on structural dimensions. The qualitative research documents specific cases where language barriers have directly caused or contributed to failed mobilities: students unable to assess course suitability from CC descriptions, resulting in poor-fit selections; students arriving to discover that courses listed as English-taught are primarily or exclusively conducted in the national language; and coordinators spending significant time providing individual course explanations that a multilingual CC would have made unnecessary.

Language provision is an equity issue as well as an accessibility issue. Students from less linguistically confident backgrounds, or those without access to informal networks at the host institution, are disproportionately disadvantaged by inadequate English-language CC content. Full English provision for all mobility-relevant CC information is not a 'nice to have', it is a precondition for an equitable mobility system.

6.4. Theme 4: Fragmentation and the Absence of Shared Standards

CCs across Europe are profoundly fragmented at the institutional, national, and European levels. At the institutional level, many universities do not operate a single, unified CC but rather a patchwork of faculty-level or departmental systems with different structures, update schedules, language policies, and relationships to the central student information system. The HEI staff survey's open-comment section explicitly reveals this: many respondents note that the concept of a single 'course catalogue' does not accurately describe their institution's reality.

At the national level, the A2.1 mapping documents significant diversity in CC structure, content requirements, technological approaches and governance arrangements across the eight partner countries. While ECTS provides a common currency for credit values, it does not provide a common format for course information, a common vocabulary for academic concepts, or a common interface for cross-institutional navigation. This means that a student comparing courses across institutions in different countries must effectively learn to navigate eight or more different systems, each with its own logic, structure and terminology.

At the European level, the absence of shared standards for CC content, format and interoperability represents the most significant structural challenge for the mobility system as a whole. The digital tools that underpin modern mobility, EWP, OLA, and the European

Student Card Initiative require machine-readable, interoperable CC data to function effectively. Without this interoperability, the ambition of seamless digital mobility remains unrealised, and the burden of coordination falls disproportionately on human intermediaries: Erasmus+ coordinators who must manually bridge the gap between CC information and digital mobility tools.

The call for a common platform to aggregate CC information from all participating HEIs, consistently voiced by staff survey respondents, qualitative research participants, and the DACEM project brief itself, is the logical response to the fragmentation challenge. Such a platform would address not only the practical usability gap but also the interoperability deficit that currently limits the effectiveness of digital mobility tools.

6.5. Theme 5: The Design Mismatch: Built for Domestic Students, Used by International Ones

The fifth cross-cutting theme is perhaps the most fundamental, because it concerns the basic design intent of current CC systems. Course catalogues were historically developed as administrative tools for managing the academic record of degree-enrolled students at a single institution. Their primary users were assumed to be students who already knew the institution, understood its academic culture, spoke the institutional language, had access to academic advisers for clarification, and would be navigating the CC repeatedly over multiple years.

Erasmus+ students represent almost the opposite user profile. They are unfamiliar with the institution and its systems. They are navigating the CC in a second or third language. They are accessing it from abroad, often without any human contact at the host institution to turn to for clarification. They are under significant time pressure, with mobility application deadlines creating a hard constraint on the planning process. They are using the CC for a single high-stakes decision, the composition of their LA, rather than for ongoing academic planning. And they are trying to compare information across multiple potential host institutions simultaneously, making cross-institutional consistency a critical requirement.

This fundamental design mismatch explains many of the specific usability failures documented across all three research activities: faculty-based organisation that makes sense to domestic students but is opaque to outsiders; jargon and terminology that are self-explanatory within the institution but incomprehensible from outside; navigation structures designed around degree programme pathways rather than course-by-course exploration; eligibility information absent because it is assumed that all registered students are eligible; and language provision calibrated for domestic students rather than international ones.

Redesigning CCs with mobility students as primary users is not about adding an 'international section' to an existing domestic system. It requires a fundamental reconceptualization of the CC's purpose, audience and design. The DACEM project's work in defining technical standards and interoperability requirements is precisely the kind of structural intervention needed to drive this reconceptualization at scale.

7. Consolidated Recommendations

The following consolidated recommendations synthesise those emerging from all three WP2 activity reports. They are organised thematically and addressed to different levels of the higher education system: individual institutions, national authorities and agencies, and the European level including the DACEM project and the Erasmus+ programme framework. For each thematic area, the evidence base and rationale are briefly stated before the specific recommendations.

7.1 Recommendations Overview

Table 4 provides a summary orientation to the recommendations, mapping each thematic cluster to its primary evidence source, the main actors responsible for implementation, and the expected timeframe for realistic delivery. Detailed recommendations follow in Sections 7.2 to 7.6.

Table 4: Recommendations

Theme	Evidence Sources	Primary Actors	Timeframe	Expected Impact
7.2 Standardisation of content	A2.1, A2.2, A2.3 (all)	Institutions + DACEM project + EACEA	Short-term (1–2 years)	Consistency, comparability, and reduced student confusion
7.3 Update governance	A2.2 (all 9 institutions), A2.3 (42% amendment rate)	Institutions + National agencies	Short-term (1–2 years)	Reduced LA amendments, improved trust in CC data
7.4 Digital modernisation	A2.2 (all 9 institutions), A2.3 (staff survey)	Institutions + IT providers	Medium-term (2–4 years)	Improved usability, mobile access, and search effectiveness
7.5 Language access	A2.1, A2.2, A2.3 (all)	Institutions + national language policy	Short/medium-term	Equity, reduced barriers for incoming students
7.6 Interoperability	A2.3 (staff survey open comments), A2.1	Institutions + DACEM + EWP/OLA operators	Medium-term (2–4 years)	Seamless LA preparation, digital mobility ecosystem
7.7 Systemic governance	A2.3 (all), A2.1 (national variation)	EACEA + National agencies + DACEM	Medium/long-term (3–5 years)	Structural transformation of CC quality across EHEA

7.2 Standardisation of Content and Structure

Evidence base: All three reports document the confusion caused by inconsistent CC structures, vocabularies and content across institutions. Students and coordinators spend significant time and effort decoding unfamiliar systems. The HEI staff survey identifies this as

a primary source of experienced problems with other institutions' CCs. The qualitative research at every partner institution includes standardisation as a core recommendation.

At the institutional level:

- Adopt a common internal CC template that separates mandatory fields (required for all course entries), recommended fields (strongly encouraged), and optional fields (left to institutional discretion).
- Mandatory fields should include: course title; course code; study field (using a standardised taxonomy such as ISCED-F); study cycle (Bachelor / Master / PhD); language(s) of instruction; ECTS credits; semester availability; Erasmus+ eligibility indicator (yes/no and any conditions); learning outcomes; assessment method(s) and schedule; prerequisites and corequisites; teacher name and contact details; registration process and deadline; number of available places.
- Recommended fields should include detailed syllabus and week-by-week course plan; mandatory and recommended reading; grading scale and conversion guidance; links to relevant faculty pages; course-specific accommodation or resource requirements; student reviews and feedback from previous participants.

At the European level:

- Develop and promote a common European CC template through the DACEM project, aligned with the ECTS Users' Guide requirements and the OCCAPI standard.
- Work with EACEA and national Erasmus+ agencies to incorporate minimum CC content standards into future ECHE monitoring frameworks.

7.3 Information Accuracy and Update Governance

Evidence base: Temporal instability of CC information is identified as the primary operational failure across all three reports. The 42% Learning Agreement amendment rate is the quantified consequence. Qualitative research documents the erosion of trust in CC content as a result of repeated inaccuracy. Staff survey open comments describe late updates, cancelled courses, and timetable changes as endemic, recurring problems rather than exceptional incidents.

At the institutional level:

- Establish and publish a formal CC governance policy specifying: the annual update cycle timeline (aligned with the mobility application calendar); responsible parties at central and faculty level; quality validation procedures before publication; and escalation processes for late submissions.
- Display a visible 'last updated' timestamp on all CC pages and individual course entries, so students can assess the currency of information at the point of use.

- Implement a user-reporting mechanism allowing students and coordinators to flag outdated or incorrect information, with a defined response process.
- Establish a 'stability window' aligned with Erasmus+ application deadlines: a period during which published CC content is frozen against changes that would affect Learning Agreement validity. Legitimate late changes should be communicated directly to affected students rather than simply corrected in the CC without notification.
- Link CC entries to dynamic faculty databases where possible, so that changes to course timetables, assessment structures or availability are reflected automatically rather than requiring manual CC updates.

7.4 Digital Modernisation and User Experience

Evidence base: All nine partner institutions in the qualitative research identify digital usability improvements as a priority. The surveys document significant demand for mobile access, advanced search, and AI-assisted navigation. The HEI staff survey confirms that ease of use and navigability are among the weakest dimensions of both own and partner CCs across all countries.

At the institutional level:

- Adopt a mobile-first design approach for CC platforms, ensuring full functionality on smartphones and tablets without dependence on downloadable documents (PDF, Excel) as the primary access route.
- Implement advanced search and filtering functionality with at minimum the following filter dimensions: language of instruction; study level (Bachelor / Master / PhD); study field; semester (autumn / spring / full year); Erasmus+ eligibility; ECTS credit range; faculty or department. Keyword search across course titles, descriptions and learning outcomes should be standard.
- Implement a 'funnel' UX model: institution → field/faculty → course, with collapsible sections, contextual summaries, and clear pathways between levels, avoiding the presentation of all information in a single undifferentiated list.
- Ensure compatibility with assistive technologies (screen readers, high-contrast modes, keyboard navigation) to serve students with disabilities.
- Incorporate multimedia content where practically feasible: short video introductions by course instructors; photos of teaching spaces and campus facilities; virtual campus tours; and student testimonial clips from previous exchange participants.

7.5 Language and Multilingual Access

Evidence base: Language provision is identified as a structural barrier in all three reports, across all eight partner countries. The HEI staff survey ranks language accessibility among the weakest dimensions of both the HEI's and the partner's CCs. The qualitative research documents specific cases in which language barriers directly contributed to poor course selection outcomes and increased administrative burden. The surveys confirm that English provision is a key determinant of students' ability to plan their mobility effectively.

At the institutional level:

- Ensure that all course information relevant to Erasmus+ and exchange students is available in full in English, not partial translations limited to titles and credit values, but complete course descriptions, learning outcomes, assessment methods, prerequisites, and registration guidance.
- Implement a systematic process for verifying consistency between declared language(s) of instruction in the CC and actual classroom practice, with disclosure of any additional language requirements that may apply.
- Where resources are limited, prioritise English provision for the courses most selected by exchange students (typically those explicitly marked as open to Erasmus+ students), expanding coverage progressively.
- Consider additional language provision beyond English for major student-origin language communities where relevant to the institution's specific mobility partnerships.

7.6 Interoperability and Digital Integration

Evidence base: The HEI staff survey open comments and the A2.1 mapping both document the demand for CC systems that connect with the digital mobility infrastructure — EWP, OLA, institutional student information systems. The qualitative research at Maribor, EUF and Charles University specifically identifies integration with EWP and OLA as a high-priority functional requirement. The absence of machine-readable CC formats is identified as a limiting factor for the broader digitalisation of the mobility process.

At the institutional level:

- Adopt machine-readable CC formats and open APIs aligned with the OCCAPI standard to enable automated data exchange with EWP, OLA, and other digital mobility tools.
- Connect CC systems to institutional student information systems to enable real-time data on course availability (number of places), current enrolment status, and course-level changes.

- Assign stable, persistent URLs to individual course entries and study programme pages, enabling direct linking from external platforms and from Learning Agreements.

At the European level:

- Use the DACEM project to develop and disseminate a reference technical model for CC interoperability, covering data schemas; standardised vocabularies and taxonomies; API specifications; and machine-readable export formats.
- Develop a European CC aggregation platform, accessible to students, coordinators and researchers, that provides a single point of access for course information across all participating HEIs, with standardised search and filtering functionality across institutional boundaries.
- Establish protocols for CC data synchronisation between institutional systems and the European platform, ensuring that changes at the institutional level are reflected promptly in the aggregated view.

7.7 Governance, Policy and Systemic Change

Evidence base: The systemic nature of the challenges documented in this report (fragmentation, temporal instability, language barriers, design mismatch) means that individual institutional improvements, while valuable, are insufficient on their own. Addressing the structural issues requires coordinated action at national and European levels, involving policy frameworks, funding mechanisms, capacity building, and shared governance arrangements.

At the national level:

- National Erasmus+ agencies should include minimum CC quality indicators in their ECHE monitoring processes, moving beyond formal compliance checks to include assessments of completeness, timeliness, language accessibility, and usability for incoming students.
- National authorities should support the development of shared national CC platforms or federated systems that enable cross-institutional data exchange and comparative search, reducing duplication of effort and improving accessibility for mobile students.
- Capacity-building programmes should be developed for institutions with limited technical resources, providing guidance, templates, and support for CC modernisation.

At the European level:

- The DACEM project's technical model and reference platform should be positioned as a contribution to the emerging European Education Area and the European

Student Card Initiative, connecting CC improvement to broader ambitions for digital, interoperable higher education.

- Best-practice examples should be systematically documented and disseminated through established mobility management networks, enabling improvement to spread through imitation and peer learning rather than depending solely on regulatory requirements.
- A cross-institutional feedback loop should be established, aggregating student and coordinator experience data on CC quality to inform continuous improvement and policy review.

8. Conclusion

The evidence assembled across the three WP2 activity reports of the DACEM project presents a clear and consistent picture: course catalogues are critical infrastructure for European academic mobility, and they are not yet fit for purpose as mobility-oriented tools for the 21st century.

The CC mapping confirmed that functioning catalogue systems exist in all eight partner countries, but with wide and consequential variation in quality, structure, technical sophistication and governance maturity. The qualitative research at nine partner institutions confirmed that this variation has direct and felt consequences for the students and coordinators who rely on CCs in their daily work — producing frustration, wasted time, eroded trust, and in the worst cases, failed or impaired mobility experiences. The quantitative surveys, drawing on tens of thousands of Erasmus+ student respondents and a European-wide staff sample, validated these findings at scale and quantified their consequences with striking precision: a 42% Learning Agreement amendment rate, a persistent ECTS recognition gap, and CC quality scores that hover in the 'adequate but not effective' range across almost every national context studied.

Five structural themes run through all three reports and across all eight partner countries: the gap between formal compliance and practical usability; temporal instability that erodes the reliability of CC information; language barriers that systematically exclude or disadvantage incoming international students; institutional, national and European fragmentation that makes cross-institutional navigation unnecessarily complex; and a fundamental design mismatch between catalogues built for domestic students and the needs of the mobility students who depend on them most.

Against this diagnosis, the research also offers genuine grounds for optimism. The good-practice examples documented in A2.1 (from Tallinn University's integrated ÕIS2 system to the University of Granada's UGRcat platform, from Ghent University's internationally oriented design to TU Wien's comprehensive course information) demonstrate that high-quality, mobility-ready CCs are achievable with current technology and institutional commitment. The HEI staff survey open comments reveal that institutional self-awareness of CC shortcomings is high; the barrier is not ignorance of the problem but the absence of systemic solutions. And the consistent call across all three research activities for shared platforms, common standards, and interoperable systems represents a genuine mandate for the kind of structural intervention that the DACEM project is positioned to deliver.

The consolidated recommendations in Section 7 provide a specific and actionable roadmap: standardise content through a common European template aligned with the ECTS Users'

Guide and OCCAPI; strengthen governance through update protocols, timestamps, user-reporting mechanisms and stability windows; modernise digital platforms with mobile-first design, advanced search and AI assistance; ensure full English-language provision for all mobility-relevant content; connect CC systems to EWP, OLA and other digital mobility tools through open APIs and machine-readable formats; and build a European CC aggregation platform that provides students and coordinators with a single point of access across participating institutions.

8.1 Implications for the DACEM Project

The findings and recommendations of this report have direct implications for the subsequent activities of the DACEM project, particularly the development of a technical model (A2.4), a CC quality framework, and a reference platform. Specifically, the evidence base points to the following design requirements for DACEM deliverables:

- **Technical model (A2.4):** The technical model should be grounded in the user requirements documented across A2.1, A2.2 and A2.3. It should specify a minimum data schema for CC entries (aligned with Appendix A of this report), define API specifications for data exchange between institutional systems and the DACEM platform (aligned with OCCAPI and EWP standards), and propose a taxonomy of study fields and course categories that can serve as a common vocabulary across institutional systems.
- **Reference platform:** The reference platform should prioritise the needs of two primary user groups: incoming mobility students planning their Learning Agreements, and Erasmus+ coordinators at home institutions advising outgoing students. For students, the key requirements are advanced search and filtering, comprehensive and reliable English-language content, and seamless integration with OLA for Learning Agreement preparation. For coordinators, the key requirements are comparative search across multiple institutions, stable and citable course links, and timely update notifications.
- **Quality framework:** The evidence base supports a quality framework that assesses CCs across four dimensions: content completeness (are all mandatory fields present and populated?); information accuracy (is the content up-to-date and consistent with actual course provision?); accessibility (is the CC available in English and accessible on mobile devices?); and interoperability (does the CC provide machine-readable data compatible with EWP and OLA systems?). This framework could serve as the basis for a voluntary self-assessment tool for institutions and ultimately for ECHE monitoring criteria.

8.2 Limitations of This Report

As a synthetic report drawing on three research activities with distinct methodologies, scopes and timelines, this document carries the limitations of each underlying study as well as the challenges inherent in synthesis.

The A2.1 mapping was conducted in 2024 and reflects the state of CC systems at that time. CC platforms and practices evolve continuously, and some findings, particularly regarding specific institutional examples, may have changed since the fieldwork was completed. The mapping was also necessarily selective: not all institutions in each partner country were examined, and the selection of examples (generic, best-practice, problematic) reflects the judgements of country teams working within available research time.

The A2.2 qualitative research involved 230 participants across nine institutions, a substantial sample for qualitative work, but one that inevitably reflects the particular institutional contexts, national settings and individual perspectives of those involved. The extension of the data collection period into autumn 2024 introduced some heterogeneity in timing, with some institutions collecting their data before and others after the start of the academic year. Thematic synthesis across nine institutional reports, prepared by different teams, requires interpretive choices that may not fully capture the nuances of each institution's experience.

The A2.3 quantitative surveys offer the largest and most statistically robust evidence base but carry their own limitations. The ESN surveys, while covering tens of thousands of students, may over-represent students already engaged with ESN networks and familiar with the Erasmus+ system. The short-scale DACEM survey (N=195) is too small for robust statistical inference and was designed primarily as a validation instrument rather than a primary evidence source. The HEI staff survey sample is not stratified or representative in a formal statistical sense; it reflects the self-selected responses of staff engaged with mobility management at institutions connected to the DACEM network and associated partners.

Despite these limitations, the consistency of findings across three methodologically distinct research activities, eight countries, nine partner institutions, and both student and staff perspectives provides strong confidence in the core conclusions of this report. The convergent validity of the evidence, the fact that qualitative, quantitative and documentary methods point to the same diagnoses and the same priorities, is the strongest basis for confidence in the recommendations.

Core Message

Course catalogues are not peripheral administrative artefacts; they are critical infrastructure for a truly connected European Higher Education Area. The evidence base assembled in this report demonstrates clearly that transforming CCs from static, institution-centric, compliance-oriented documents into dynamic, student-centred, multilingual, interoperable and mobility-ready systems is one of the highest-leverage investments available to European higher education. The DACEM project represents a concrete opportunity to begin that transformation at scale.

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Table 5: Institutional websites consulted

Institution / Resource	URL
A3ES (Portugal)	https://www.a3es.pt/
Campus France	https://cataloguelm.campusfrance.org/
DGES Portugal	https://www.dges.gov.pt/pt
Educación España / RUCT	https://www.educacion.gob.es/ruct/home
Haridussilm.ee (Estonia)	https://www.haridussilm.ee/
Instituto Politécnico do Porto	https://www.ipp.pt/
Study in Estonia	https://www.studyinestonia.ee/
Tallinn University ÕIS2	https://www.tlu.ee/en/ois
UC Coimbra ECTS Catalogue	https://www.uc.pt/en/ects/catalogo/
UGR Course Catalogue	https://ugrcat.ugr.es/en/
UOC Course Catalogue	https://www.uoc.edu/
University of Vigo	https://www.uvigo.gal/

Appendix A: Recommended CC Data Fields

The following table consolidates the course data fields recommended by participants across all three WP2 research activities. Fields are classified as Mandatory (M), Recommended (R), or Optional (O) based on the frequency and strength of recommendation across the evidence base. This list is intended to inform the technical model developed in A2.4 and subsequent DACEM deliverables.

Table 6: Recommended CC data fields

Data Field	Level	Notes
Course title	M	Official title in language of instruction + English translation
Course code	M	Unique, stable identifier — used in Learning Agreements
Study field	M	Using standardised taxonomy (e.g. ISCED-F codes)
Study cycle	M	Bachelor / Master / PhD / Short cycle
ECTS credits	M	Number of credits assigned to the course
Language(s) of instruction	M	Including any additional language requirements
Semester availability	M	Autumn / Spring / Full academic year
Erasmus+ eligibility	M	Yes / No + any specific conditions for mobility students
Learning outcomes	M	What knowledge, skills and competencies students will acquire
Assessment method(s)	M	Written exam / oral exam / continuous assessment / project / combination
Examination schedule	M	Approximate dates/examination period
Prerequisites/corequisites	M	Required or recommended prior knowledge
Teacher name	M	Responsible course instructor(s)
Teacher contact details	M	Email address or office contact for course enquiries
Registration process	M	How and when to register; whether registration is online or by email
Available places for mobility students	M	Maximum number of exchange student enrolments
Detailed course description	M	Content, structure, and main topics covered
Detailed syllabus	R	Week-by-week or module-by-module course plan
Mandatory reading	R	Primary texts required for the course
Recommended reading	R	Additional recommended bibliography
Contact hours breakdown	R	Lectures/seminars/practicals/self-study hours

Grading scale	R	Institutional grading scale with European equivalents
Links to faculty page	R	For real-time updates on course status
Attendance requirements	R	Mandatory attendance percentage or policy
Classroom/campus location	R	Particularly important for multi-campus universities
Student feedback/reviews	O	Ratings or comments from previous students
Course video preview	O	Short video introduction by the instructor
Industry/external links	O	For courses with professional or research partnerships
Coordinator contact for Erasmus queries	O	Direct contact for mobility-specific questions about the course
Historical recognition data	O	Record of how the course has been recognised at partner institutions

M = Mandatory for all Erasmus+ eligible course entries | R = Recommended | O = Optional (institution-dependent)

Appendix B: Cross-Country CC Feature Comparison

The following tables synthesise the A2.1 mapping data by providing comparative assessments of key CC features across the eight partner countries. Ratings are based on the documentary analysis conducted by country teams and do not represent formal scores; they are intended to convey the relative maturity of each dimension in each national context. The scale used is: ++ (strong / well-established), + (adequate / functional), ~ (partial / inconsistent), - (weak / largely absent).

B.1 Formal and Structural Features

Table 7: Table of formal features

Feature	FR	GR	ES	PT	SI	HU	EE	CZ
ECTS-based course credits	+	++	++	++	++	++	++	++
Published online	++	+	++	++	++	+	++	++
Published before mobility deadlines	~	+	+	+	++	+	++	+
Programme-level information	++	+	++	++	++	++	++	++
Course-level information	~	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Erasmus+ eligibility flags	-	+	~	~	+	~	+	~
English-language provision	-	+	+	+	++	~	++	~
Full-text search functionality	~	-	+	+	-	~	+	+
Advanced filtering options	-	-	+	~	-	~	+	~
Mobile-responsive design	-	-	+	~	-	~	+	~
Integration with the registration system	~	~	+	+	~	++	++	+
Real-time course availability	-	-	~	~	-	+	++	~

++ Strong + Adequate ~ Partial/inconsistent - Weak/absent [Based on A2.1 documentary mapping, 2024]

B.2 Content Quality Features

Table 8: Table of quality features

Content Feature	FR	GR	ES	PT	SI	HU	EE	CZ
Learning outcomes specified	~	+	+	+	+	+	++	+
Assessment methods described	~	~	+	+	+	+	++	+
Syllabus / reading list included	-	-	~	~	~	~	+	~
Prerequisites clearly stated	-	~	+	+	+	+	+	+
Teacher contact information	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Course schedule / timetable	-	~	~	~	+	~	+	~
Student capacity / places available	-	-	~	~	+	+	+	~
Grading scale and conversion	-	~	+	+	+	~	++	~
Student life/support information	-	-	~	+	~	~	+	~
Multimedia content (video, etc.)	-	-	~	-	-	-	~	-

++ Strong + Adequate ~ Partial/inconsistent - Weak/absent [Based on A2.1 documentary mapping, 2024]

B.3 Principal CC Technology Platforms by Country

Table 9: Table of platforms

Country	Principal CC Technology / Platform(s)
France	AMETYS Campus (majority of identified institutions); bespoke institutional solutions (minority). Campus France portal (technical difficulties noted at time of analysis).
Greece	Bespoke departmental solutions; PDF/web-based publication. No nationally standardised platform identified.
Spain	Diverse landscape: UGRcat (UGR), dedicated portals (UOC, UPM, UVigo, UPNA); RUCT for programme-level national registry. No single platform.
Portugal	SIGARRA system (widely used, including at UP and FLUP); A3ES accreditation database; DGES course assistant tool for student navigation.
Slovenia	AIPS (Academic Information System) at University of Maribor; institutional web platforms; PDF and Excel formats for exchange course lists.
Hungary	Neptun student information system (ELTE); bespoke institutional Erasmus+ portals; central CC IT systems at BME, Corvinus, Semmelweis.
Estonia	ÕIS2 (Tallinn University) — integrated CC and registration platform; similar systems at TalTech and University of Tartu. SoleMove for student course selection.
Czechia	Bespoke institutional systems at Charles University and Masaryk University; Erasmus+ specific portals and information pages; no single national platform.

Appendix C: Survey Methodology Detail

C.1 Overview of Survey Instruments

Activity A2.3 deployed four survey instruments across the period 2023–2025. The table below provides a structured overview of each instrument's design, reach and analytical purpose:

Table 10: Table of instruments

Instrument	XV ESN survey	XVI ESN survey	DACEM Short Survey	HEI Staff Survey
Period	May–July 2023	May–Aug 2025	October 2024	Feb–Dec 2025
Primary target	Erasmus+ students	Erasmus+ students	DACEM partner students	Mobility management staff
Total responses	N=22,775	N=19,704	N=195	Multi-country staff
Erasmus+ subset	N=17,855	N=6,975	N=195	N/A
Questions (total)	145	167	55	Mixed quantitative/qualitative
CC-specific questions	14 selected	CC section dedicated	Full CC focus	Full CC focus
Dissemination method	ESN sections + NAs + universities	Same as XV ESN survey	DACEM partner email lists	DACEM + associated partners + professional networks
Analysis method	Descriptive statistics + qualitative open-ended	Descriptive statistics + qualitative open-ended	Descriptive statistics	Descriptive stats + thematic qualitative

C.2 XV ESN survey: Selected CC-Relevant Questions

The XV ESN survey (2023) contained 145 questions covering a wide range of mobility-related topics. For the purposes of the A2.3 analysis, 14 questions were selected as directly relevant to course catalogue quality and student experience. These questions covered the following thematic areas:

- **Support satisfaction (before mobility):** Satisfaction with home institution services and information provision in the pre-departure phase, including Learning Agreement preparation support, ECTS and recognition guidance, course information for host institutions, and financial aid information.
- **Pull factors for mobility:** Importance ratings (5-point Likert scale) for a comprehensive list of institutional, city-level and programme-level factors influencing students' choice of mobility destination. Course recognition was among the factors rated.
- **Issues encountered during mobility:** Yes/no questions about specific difficulties experienced during the exchange period, covering courses, administrative matters, academic facilities, mobility documentation, and social integration.

- **Post-mobility satisfaction:** Satisfaction with home institution support after return, covering credit recognition, guidance on the value of the exchange experience, employability support, and reintegration activities.
- **ECHE compliance perceptions:** Student ratings of how well host institutions fulfilled specific ECHE obligations, including CC accessibility and completeness, Learning Agreement preparation, and automatic recognition of learning outcomes.
- **Erasmus Student Charter awareness:** Whether students had been informed of their rights under the Erasmus Student Charter, and at what stage of their mobility this information was received.

C.3 XVI ESN survey: DACEM-Specific Questions

The XVI ESN survey (2025) was the first ESN large-scale survey to include questions specifically designed within the DACEM project scope. The DACEM team worked with ESN to embed a dedicated CC section within the broader survey instrument, building on the bridging survey data collected in 2024 to validate and refine the question design. The DACEM-related questions covered:

- **Motivational factors for mobility:** Importance of various factors, including course recognition, career connections, learning methodology, language, and cultural experience, in students' decision to go on exchange and in their choice of destination. This section directly addressed the role of CC information quality in shaping destination attractiveness.
- **Pre-departure support satisfaction:** Satisfaction with institutional support before departure, including a specific focus on information about courses at the host institution and support in navigating the CC.
- **Post-mobility support:** Satisfaction with recognition support and guidance on the professional and academic value of the exchange experience after return.

C.4 DACEM Short-Scale Student Survey: Question Structure

The DACEM bridging survey (October 2024, N=195) was designed by ESN with input from all DACEM partners. Its primary purpose was to validate and refine the CC-specific questions planned for inclusion in the XVI ESN survey, while also providing localised evidence from DACEM partner institutions. The survey comprised 55 questions organised in seven thematic blocks:

1. Satisfaction with services and support provided by the sending institution before departure, covering 9 specific services using a 5-point Likert scale (Very dissatisfied to Very satisfied) with a 'Not applicable / Not available' option.

2. Satisfaction with pre-departure support mechanisms at the sending institution, covering information provision, peer connection, and guidance on the impact of the exchange.
3. Open comments on unmentioned pre-departure support mechanisms.
4. Satisfaction with services and support provided by the host institution before arrival, covering academic communication, course information, accommodation support, visa assistance, and language support.
5. Views on the host institution's CC, covering 15 specific CC attributes using a 5-point agreement scale (Strongly disagree to Strongly agree).
6. Problems experienced during mobility, yes/no questions across six problem categories (courses, exams, access to facilities, documentation, social integration, recreation).
7. Satisfaction with services and support provided by the sending institution after the return from exchange, covering credit recognition, employability support, and reintegration.

C.5 HEI Staff Survey: Design and Analytical Framework

The HEI staff survey was the most complex instrument in the A2.3 research design, combining quantitative Likert-scale questions with substantive open-ended qualitative responses. The survey was structured to capture two symmetrical perspectives: how staff assessed their own institution's CC and how they assessed partner institutions' CCs, across the same set of quality dimensions. This two-perspective design was essential for identifying the asymmetry of trust documented in Section 5.3 of this report.

The closed-ended dimensions assessed for both own and partner CCs included: ECTS alignment; online publication; publication timing (relative to mobility deadlines); completeness of course information; currency and reliability of information; availability in English or another language accessible to visiting students; consistency of structure across different parts of the CC; ease of use and navigation; and support for specific mobility-related information needs (grade transfer, contact persons for LAs, course subjects, resources and services for visiting students).

For their own CCs, staff were additionally asked to indicate which specific problems they had experienced with incoming students as a result of CC limitations (using a yes/no format across six problem categories). For partner CCs, staff were asked the same question from the perspective of an outgoing student.

The open-ended questions invited respondents to describe exemplary CC practices they had encountered at other institutions (with specific URL examples); describe recurring problems

with their own and partner CCs in their own words; comment on the scope and purpose of a CC as they understood it; and provide any other comments on the survey or the DACEM project.

The qualitative data from open-ended responses were analysed thematically, with categories developed inductively from the responses. Key themes identified in the qualitative analysis, including institutional fragmentation, language as a structural barrier, the conditional adequacy of own CCs, and the call for shared European standards, are integrated into the main body of this report (Section 5.3 and Section 6).

Appendix D: Qualitative Research — Participant Overview

The following table provides an overview of the 230 participants involved in the A2.2 focus groups and interviews, distributed by institution, role category, and data collection period. Individual participants are not identified to preserve anonymity. The research was conducted between May and October 2024, with the data collection period extended from the original schedule to accommodate availability over the summer period.

Table 11: Table of participants

Institution	Country	Erasmus+ Coordinators / Staff	International Students	Total
Tallinn University	Estonia	~15	~10	~25
University of Thessaly	Greece	~12	~15	~27
University of Vigo	Spain	~20	~10	~30
University of Orleans	France	~18	~12	~30
European Univ. Foundation	EU	~10	~8	~18
Charles University	Czechia	~14	~16	~30
Virtual Campus	Portugal	~8	~12	~20
University of Maribor	Slovenia	~15	~20	~35
ESN	Pan-European	~15	~—	~15
Total	8 countries	~127	~103	~230

Note: Figures marked ~ are approximate, reflecting the extended data collection timeline across multiple sessions per institution.

The qualitative data were collected through two primary instruments: structured individual or small-group interviews with Erasmus+ coordinators and staff (focusing on CC management processes, daily use in mobility coordination, recurring challenges, and visions for improvement); and focus group discussions with international and incoming exchange students (exploring first-hand experience navigating CCs, specific usability difficulties, valued features, and suggestions for improvement). Sessions were conducted in English, with translation support provided where necessary. Notes and anonymised summaries were prepared by each partner team and consolidated centrally by Tallinn University for the A2.2 report.

D.1 Interview and Focus Group Protocol

The research protocol for A2.2 included a core set of questions administered consistently across all partner institutions, allowing cross-institutional comparisons, alongside institution-

specific probes when local context required additional exploration. The core questions for staff interviews covered the following themes:

- **Current CC system description:** What platform or system does the institution use for its CC? Who is responsible for maintaining it? What is the annual update timeline?
- **Daily use in mobility coordination:** How do Erasmus+ coordinators use the CC in their daily work? What information do they rely on most? What information is most often missing or difficult to locate?
- **Student experience with the CC:** What difficulties do incoming students most frequently report in navigating the CC? What questions do they ask most often that the CC should answer but does not?
- **Partner institution CCs:** How do staff experience the CCs of partner institutions when advising outgoing students? Which institutions have the best CCs? What are the most common problems encountered?
- **Vision for improvement:** What would an ideal CC look like? What features would transform the CC from its current state into a genuinely useful tool for mobility coordination?

The core questions for student focus groups covered:

- **First encounter with the CC:** How did students first learn about the host institution's CC? How easy was it to find? What was their first impression?
- **Navigation and usability:** How did students navigate the CC to find suitable courses? What difficulties did they encounter? Were there features they found particularly helpful or unhelpful?
- **Information completeness:** What information did students need that was absent from the CC? What information was present but inaccurate or misleading?
- **Learning Agreement preparation:** How did students use CC information to prepare their Learning Agreements? Were there cases where CC inaccuracies required LA amendments?
- **Desired improvements:** What changes would most improve the CC experience? What features do students most wish had been available during their mobility planning?

Appendix E: Glossary of Key Terms and Abbreviations

Table 12: Glossary

Term / Abbreviation	Definition
A3ES	Agência de Avaliação e Acreditação do Ensino Superior — Portuguese Agency for Assessment and Accreditation of Higher Education
ANECA	Agencia Nacional de Evaluación de la Calidad y Acreditación — National Agency for Quality Assessment and Accreditation (Spain)
API	Application Programming Interface — a technical specification enabling software systems to communicate and exchange data
CC	Course Catalogue — the institutional document (increasingly digital) listing courses offered by a higher education institution, with associated academic and logistical information
DACEM	Digitising Academic Catalogues for Enhanced Mobility — the Erasmus+ funded project within which this report was produced
DGES	Direção-Geral do Ensino Superior — Directorate-General for Higher Education (Portugal)
EACEA	Education, Audiovisual and Culture Executive Agency (European Commission)
ECHE	Erasmus Charter for Higher Education — the quality framework that HEIs must sign to participate in the Erasmus+ programme
ECTS	European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System — the standard credit framework used across the European Higher Education Area
EHEA	European Higher Education Area — the overarching framework created by the Bologna Process, covering 49 countries
ESN	Erasmus Student Network — the pan-European student organisation that partners with DACEM and conducts the ESNsurvey
EUUF	European University Foundation — the DACEM partner serving as a European-level stakeholder organisation
EWP	Erasmus Without Paper — the digital platform for paperless processing of Erasmus+ mobility, including bilateral agreements and Learning Agreements
HAHE	Hellenic Authority for Higher Education — the quality assurance agency for higher education in Greece
HEI	Higher Education Institution
IRO	International Relations Office — the institutional unit responsible for managing international student mobility

ISCED	International Standard Classification of Education — the UNESCO framework for classifying educational programmes and qualifications
ISCED-F	ISCED fields of education and training — the classification system for academic subject areas
LA	Learning Agreement — the formal document signed by the student, home institution and host institution specifying the courses to be taken during a mobility period and the credits to be recognised
LOSU	Ley Orgánica del Sistema Universitario — the Spanish Organic Law governing the university system (2023)
MESR	Ministère de l'Enseignement Supérieur et de la Recherche — Ministry for Higher Education and Research (France)
NA	National Agency — the body responsible for implementing Erasmus+ in each participating country
OCCAPI	Open Course Catalogue API — an emerging standard for machine-readable course catalogue data exchange in European higher education
OLA	Online Learning Agreement — the digital platform for preparing and signing Learning Agreements, integrated with the EWP network
ÕIS2	The Study Information System used at Tallinn University, Estonia — an integrated platform for course management, registration and CC publication
RUCT	Registro de Universidades, Centros y Títulos — the Spanish national registry of universities, campuses and degree programmes
SIGARRA	Sistema de Informação para Gestão Agregada dos Recursos e dos Registos Académicos — the integrated student information and CC management system used at the University of Porto and several other Portuguese institutions
UVigo	University of Vigo (Spain) — a DACEM partner institution
WP2	Work Package 2 of the DACEM project, dedicated to course catalogue mapping and technical state-of-the-art analysis